
EMPOWERING REGIONAL SUSTAINABILITY AND INCLUSIVITY THROUGH GREENING TVET

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Abstract

The growing imperative for sustainable development has intensified the transformation of Technical and Vocational Education and Training (TVET) systems towards green, digital, and inclusive competencies. This study examines the extent of green skills integration in TVET institutions across selected Asia-Pacific countries focusing on institutional practices, skill gaps, industry collaboration, and implementation challenges. A descriptive-exploratory design was employed using survey data from TVET professionals participating in a regional capacity-building program in Thailand. Findings indicate that the regional TVET systems are in a transitional stage of green transformation, with moderate to high integration of green technical skills, circular economy concepts, climate-resilient practices, and sustainability governance. However, significant gaps persist in circular economy/resource efficiency skills, digital-green competencies, and applied green innovation. Institutional practices are strongest in green campus initiatives and curriculum integration while inclusive industry partnerships remain limited. Collaboration with industry is largely concentrated on internships and training with weaker engagement in research and policy development. Employment outcomes from green skills training are perceived as moderate, thereby reflecting an emerging but still developing green labor market linkage. Key challenges include limited funding, insufficient faculty expertise, weak industry linkages, and inadequate infrastructure. The study underscores the need for a more integrated ecosystem approach to strengthen TVET capacity and accelerate inclusive green skills development in the region.

Key Words: Greening TVET, Digital Transformation, Sustainability, Green Paradigm, Green Economy, Green Transformation, Circular Economy

1. INTRODUCTION

The road towards sustainable development has been dealt with a constant rough patch that many countries, especially those within the Asia-Pacific (APAC) region, have come into terms over the years. This can be attributed to the impact of the global shift from Industry 4.0 to Industry 5.0 that stemmed from the urgent need to revolutionize the way we capacitate and empower our present and future human capital (International Labour Organization, 2019; Wickramasinghe et al., 2025). This milestone ushered in a new era of innovation in which nations must rigorously adapt to the evolving demands of the modern labor market.

However, as humanity climbs further towards its prime and opulence with the design and creation of numerous technological advancements, several challenges have also surfaced which raises concerns on the stability and welfare of the present and future generations. Sustainability and inclusivity have become major considerations with economies transitioning to green practices and digitalization (Wambura, 2024; Quimba

et al., 2023). Part of this endeavor is poverty reduction in which the region unfortunately is falling behind (United Nations Development Programme & Asian Development Bank, n.d.). This can be attributed to the disparities in the demographic characteristics of the countries with the growing number of young people that are expected to join the workforce in the coming years.

Another persisting collective issue that the Asia-Pacific region is facing are the climate crisis and the ecological degradation (Carbon Brief, n.d.; History.com, n.d.). Previous studies show that 40% of the total world employment depends largely on ecosystem services. The greenhouse gas emissions (GHG) have also increased significantly by 33% while the material extraction is also rising at 62% worldwide (International Labour Organization, 2019). Moreover, experts are expecting that by 2030, more hours will be lost due to heat stress. This is equivalent to 72 million full-time jobs over time (International Labour Organization, 2019).

Moreso, the urgent need to transition to a low carbon economy to effectively address both the economic and environmental issues paved the way in building new industries as enterprises start adopting new technologies and more sustainable practices in their operations (Martínez, 2024; Zilberstein, 2023). In fact, even the Association of Southeast Asian Nations (ASEAN) created the **ASEAN Economic Community Blueprint** and **ASEAN Declaration on Promoting Green Jobs for Equity and Inclusive Growth** to actively promote green employment in clean energy, energy efficiency and green buildings and urban planning (ASEAN, n.d.). The concept of the green paradigm has become synonymous with the green economy as countries continue to leverage its strongest potential.

With this, the Technical and Vocational Education and Training (TVET) plays a pivotal role in setting the tone towards the realization of sustainable development and inclusive growth across the Asia-Pacific region. As the fundamental mechanism in facilitating skills development, TVET has the capacity to empower the current and future workforce with the required competencies in order to effectively adapt to the demands of green economies and Industry 5.0 (UNESCO-UNEVOC, 2017; UNESCO-UNEVOC, 2023). Aside from the technical and vocational skills, the modern-day TVET involves the integration of environmental awareness, sustainability principles, and inclusive practices that will ensure that no sector of the society is being left behind.

On the regional aspect, the 16 **Colombo Plan Staff College (CPSC)** member countries are also making a significant stride in aligning their TVET systems with the objectives of global sustainability and inclusivity. However, variations can be observed in terms of policy implementation, institutional capacity, and access to resources (Majumdar, 2021; ESCAP, n.d.). And these factors can be challenging in terms of fully operationalizing the greening initiatives within the TVET sector. Therefore, the disparities highlighted the need to further assess the manner in which the TVET institutions across the region are responding to the pressing demand for green skills and inclusive development.

Hence, this study aims to assess how TVET systems within the CPSC member countries are working towards the goal of empowering regional sustainability and inclusivity through the effective integration of green practices in the region. Specifically, it showcases the ways and means in which these nations are upholding their responsibility in promoting sustainability principles. These are based on the TVET institutions' curriculum development activities, capacity-building initiatives for trainers and institutions, and industry partnerships for green employment as reported by the participants from the CPSC Regional Program on *Promoting Green Research, Green Skills, Sustainability, and Inclusiveness in TVET System of Asia-Pacific Countries* that was held from February 23 to 27 in Thailand. By identifying the key trends, challenges, and opportunities, the study seeks to provide relevant insights and valuable recommendations

in strengthening the role of TVET towards a resilient, inclusive, and environmentally sustainable future for the Asia-Pacific region (UNESCO-UNEVOC, 2015; United Nations, 2025).

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 THE EVOLVING GLOBAL ENVIRONMENTAL LANDSCAPE AND THE CALL FOR A UNIFIED CLIMATE ACTION

Since 1992, the international lens has ultimately focused on the perennial challenges brought about by environmental degradation, social disparities, and economic instability (United Nations, 2025; World Nuclear Association, n.d.). Numerous vulnerabilities in the global, social and economic systems have come to light as countries grapple with the effects of the rapid industrialization, population growth, and urbanization that place increasing pressure on our natural resources (Carbon Brief, n.d.; History.com, n.d.). Productivity, employment, and the livelihoods of millions, particularly those from the vulnerable communities, were highly affected by climate change, biodiversity loss, and the intensification of extreme weather events.

But contrary to popular belief, experts have clarified that the issue of climate change has long been plaguing the Earth with greenhouse gases warming the oceans as early as 1800s (Carbon Brief, n.d.). Moreover, the moment that human society has begun to industrialize, the accelerated combustion of fossil fuels, deforestation, and large-scale resource extraction have also intensified the accumulation of greenhouse gases in the atmosphere. The cumulative impact of the centuries worth of industrial activities has disrupted the natural cycles and ecosystems as it also amplifies the social and economic vulnerabilities of nations all over the world.

Going through the course of history, the long-term alteration in the Earth's climate and weather patterns can be traced back to centuries ago. However, this crisis was seen before as a theory rather than a threat that presents a host of catastrophic consequences. It was in the 1820s when the French mathematician and physicist Joseph Fourier cited that the energy that reaches the planet as sunlight must be balanced by the energy that returns to space (History.com, n.d.). He further reasoned that some of this energy is being held within the atmosphere which keeps the Earth warm. Fourier described the atmosphere as, "*...the Earth's thin covering of air that acts the way a glass greenhouse would.*" This glass wall then resembles a warm greenhouse when it traps the energy inside.

The presence of coal gas such as carbon dioxide (CO²), methane, and volatile hydrocarbons in the atmosphere was corroborated by the Irish scientist John Tyndall in his experiments during the 1860s (History.com, n.d.). The CO² in particular was described by Tyndall as somewhat resembling a sponge due to its capacity to absorb multiple wavelengths of sunlight. And with the onset of the Industrial Revolution, British engineer Guy Stewart Callender also showcased in his calculations that doubling the CO² in the atmosphere could warm the Earth by 2°C (3.6°F).

Since then, countries have experienced a steady but sharp increase in the global temperature rate. Its effect became more prominent with the widespread cases of drought and wildfires that were experienced even by the most progressive countries in the world with the likes of the United States. In 1989, the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC) was created by the United Nations in order to present a scientific view of climate change and its political and economic impacts (United Nations, 2025). With the growing international attention that this environmental issue has amassed over the years, researchers have

Since 1973

predicted a strong possibility of severe heat waves, droughts, and more powerful hurricanes that are fueled by the rising sea surface temperatures in the days to come.

Hence, the establishment of the **Conference of the Parties (COP)** as part of the **United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change (UNFCCC)** has been the global answer to stabilize the concentrations of greenhouse gases in the atmosphere at levels that would avoid the dangerous anthropogenic or human-caused climate change (UNFCCC, n.d.; World Nuclear Association, n.d.). Since 1995, a series of annual COP meetings has ensued to continuously address the historic greenhouse gas emissions. The turning point in this initiative is the adoption of the Paris Agreement during the COP21 in 2015. This international treaty was premised on the goal that is to limit the increase in global temperature to well below 2° above pre-industrial levels. This subsequently resulted in the publication of the **Nationally Determined Contribution (NDC)** documents every five years which set out the countries' own plans for emission reductions, and their methods in which these shall be achieved.

With the culmination of COP30 in 2025, participating governments have highlighted the lasting impact of climate change across all sectors and key systems ranging from energy and transport to food and health, from industry and finance to land, ocean, and education, among others. Likewise, the discourse about climate actions was structured based on the six thematic axes namely: 1) *transitioning energy, industry, and transport*; 2) *stewarding forests, oceans, and biodiversity*; 3) *transforming agriculture and food systems*; 4) *building resilience for cities, infrastructure and water*; 5) *fostering human and social development*; and 6) *the final cross-cutting axis of unleashing enablers and accelerators including finance, technology and capacity-building* (NewClimate Institute, 2026; United Nations, 2025).

In terms of **transitioning energy, industry, and transport (Axis 1)**, COP reported a strong but inconsistent momentum with clean power and electrification being constrained by the slow grid upgrades, concentrated investments, stalled efficiency and rising methane. Unfortunately, key industrial technologies are deemed costly and fragmented with their unclear standards. In addition to this, energy access and planning the fair transitions for the regions that are still reliant on fossil fuel industries are still considered as major gaps in the process.

Axis 2 (Stewarding Forests, Oceans, and Biodiversity) on the other hand presented the implementation of nature-based solutions (NbS) that are scalable and investable by effectively reducing risks, creating jobs, and driving resilient growth that are measurable and scalable for the investors and policymakers. In this area, it was noted that progress appears to be uneven which can be attributed to continued ecosystem loss, limited effectiveness of protected areas, and insufficient long-term finance for restoration and NbS.

On the aspect of **transforming agriculture and food system (Axis 3)**, the UN highlighted that the progress remains uneven due to chronic underinvestment, widespread land degradation, lack of enabling policies and finance incentives, and limited support for smallholders and food Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs). However, this does not diminish the fact that land restoration, strengthening of the food system, and equitable access to nutrition are all vital in increasing resilience.

As far as **building resilience for cities, infrastructure, and water (Axis 4)** is concerned, the COP30 has showcased a strong commitment to accelerate the deployment of resilient urban planning, climate-smart infrastructure, nature-based urban solutions, and enhanced building standards. Moreover, the effective integration of resilience metrics, community-driven planning, and digital tools that will equip the cities to assess risks and design equitable solutions empowered national governments, cities, multilateral banks, and

the private sector by effectively developing climate-resilient infrastructure and promoting inclusive and sustainable urban development.

Human development also plays an important role in addressing the climate challenges. This is one of the reasons as to why **Axis 5 or fostering human and social development** required the prioritization of skills development as part of the transition process for the empowerment of the mandatory climate education. In the course of its implementation however, it was observed that vulnerabilities such as limited support for green skills and inadequate climate-health measures hinder the green transition. Greater investment is then essential to guarantee shared benefits so that no one will be truly left behind.

Lastly, in terms of **unleashing enablers and accelerators including on financing, technology, and capability building (Axis 6)**, relevant themes such as growing country and SME focus, use of market mechanisms, harmonization of standards, and de-risking to lower the cost of capital were considered priority actions as part of the Baku to Belem Roadmap. However, these initiatives were met with uncertainty due to the high cost and limited institutional capacity for enablers and accelerators especially for a number of developing countries. This calls for a fairer access to all, de-risking to lower the cost of capital, and support the advancement of project pipelines for climate solutions for better cascading and implementation.

As we approach the new era in our pursuit of sustainable and inclusive development, the Asia-Pacific region in particular has been in the forefront of the global discussion due to its heavy reliance on coal and gas. Amidst its strong potential with its rich cultural heritage and megabiodiversity, the region has been plagued by the climate crisis given its strategic yet vulnerable location. Extreme weather events, sea-level rise, and flooding are some of these natural and even man-made disasters that have been posing significant threats to the socio-economic development of the APAC countries. Nevertheless, the dual challenge of sustaining economic growth and transitioning to clean energy highlights the urgent need for renewable energy deployment and capacity building initiatives (CARE Climate Change, n.d.). And this is where the role of the green paradigm fits into the narrative.

2.2 THE EMERGENCE OF GREEN PARADIGM AS A DRIVER FOR SUSTAINABLE AND INCLUSIVE DEVELOPMENT

The concept of the **Green Paradigm** has long been championed by nations as a crucial part of their national development agenda. The term green paradigm is described as a set of concepts that support sustainable progress while taking into consideration the requirements of both humanity and the natural environment (Martínez, 2024; Zilberstein, 2023). Shifting from the traditional point of view where technology was viewed as a possible threat to mankind to the proactive utilization of modern innovation to improve the quality of human life, the green paradigm nurtures the human-nature relationship while finding ways to alleviate the critical effects of climate change on communities.

With the continuing environmental degradation, countries are now resorting to low-carbon economies and societies. The primary objective is the achievement of overall sustainability, robust market competition and employment, signal sustainable transformations, and mitigation of long-term climate change impact in the region. However, environmental changes, shifting priorities in the environmental policies, technology and innovations as well as changes in the market and the consumer habits are perpetually shaping the current global landscape as drivers of change. Moreover, the development of a low carbon world as the ultimate goal will eventually lead to reduced emissions, higher economic productivity, and inclusive growth. With this, the concept of **green economy** under the green paradigm was coined. **Green economy** pertains to the economic policy framework that is designed to curb the emission, reduce environmental risks, safeguard

ecosystems, increase resilience of energy systems through effective governance, harness low-carbon technologies, and promote sustainable practices.

However, the full adoption of the imperatives of the green economy also presents a unique set of challenges and opportunities. Despite the fact that the Asia-Pacific region has made a remarkable economic growth in the recent decades which resulted to the alleviation of its high poverty rate and cementing its legacy as a global economic powerhouse, its dependence on resource-intensive industries such as agriculture, mining, and manufacturing has made an impact on the natural resources and ecosystems. Rapid industrialization, urbanization, and increased consumption yielded to heightened pollution levels and exacerbated the impacts of climate change.

Green Transformation then facilitates the smooth transition and advancement of the **Circular Economy (CE)**. As a viable strategy for supporting sustainable growth, CE employs recycling, reusing, and refurbishing to effectively reduce waste, lower greenhouse gas emissions, and curb pollution. As the cornerstone of the green economy, CE also enables the establishment of green-tech startups and new ventures that utilize and operate environmentally sustainable business models for social and economic development (Martínez, 2024).

With these, the demand for skills have become more pronounced as countries navigate expertly through the complexities of the transition process from traditional to green and inclusive economies. Renewable energy adoption, and the application of circular economy practices must be facilitated in order to build sustainable production systems. Through these, we are equipping a highly capable workforce that are empowered with both technical and transversal competencies that are aligned with the industry needs. The focus is not merely on the green technical skills but also the digital capabilities, innovation skills, and a complete understanding of the sustainability principles that will support the long-term environmental and socio-economic goals.

The green transformation also paved the way for opportunities in the form of employment and entrepreneurship especially in emerging green sectors such as clean energy, sustainable agriculture, and eco-friendly manufacturing (Zilberstein, 2023; Quimba et al., 2023). However, several disparities were observed specifically with the unequal access to quality education and training, limited institution capacity, and imminent gaps in the implementation of national policies (ESCAP, n.d.; Asian Development Bank, n.d.). Such situations highlight the need for a more inclusive approach to skills development to ensure equal access for women, youth, and the marginalized sectors.

As we summon the collective effort in the advancement of sustainable and inclusive development, it is quite clear that the effectiveness of the green paradigm is hinged directly not only on the policy direction and technological innovation, but also on the readiness of the human capital to continuously adapt and proactively respond to transformations this process entails. As complex as the green transition and green paradigm might appear, these demand a fully equipped workforce that is capacitated with the relevant skills, empowered by inclusive opportunities, and supported by responsive education and training systems.

2.3 ENABLING THE GREEN ALIGNMENT THROUGH THE REGIONAL GREENING TVET INITIATIVES

On September 18, 2019, the United Nations Secretary General released the Climate Action for Jobs Initiative. This provides an actionable roadmap for the facilitation of people's jobs and well-being during the transition to a carbon-neutral economy as part of the green paradigm (International Labour Organization, 2019). And the Asia-Pacific region alone hosted more than 60% of the global workforce.

Along with the perennial issue of extreme poverty with income level averaging at US\$1.90 per person per day, the transition process would entail major societal changes and substantial economic risks.

Unfortunately, the APAC region is also facing serious critical repercussions as it falls behind the accomplishment of the 17 Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). The region after all is highly vulnerable to sea level rise, glacier melt, temperature increase, and intensified storms and floods. Such calamities highly affect the agriculture, fisheries, forestry sectors as they impact the countries' food security, poverty, and livelihood disproportionately. Moreover, these impact the 850 million regional workers who are dependent on the natural systems for their livelihoods.

To address this major global concern, the concept of **Green Jobs** was designed to contribute to the preservation and restoration of the environment (International Labour Organization, 2019; UNESCO-UNEVOC, 2017). This encompasses both the traditional sectors such as manufacturing and construction and the emerging green sectors like renewable energy and energy efficiency. Furthermore, the UN described the green jobs as quality, decent jobs that are in line with the four strategic objectives namely: *1) set and promote standards and fundamental principles and rights at work; 2) create greater opportunities for women and men to obtain decent employment and income; 3) enhance the coverage and effectiveness of social protection; and 4) strengthen tripartism (government, workers', and employers' organizations) and social dialogue.* However, a complete understanding of what green skills are also needed to adequately diffuse the workforce in preparation to the full adoption of the green jobs in the industry.

The term **Green Skills** is defined as a combination of technical knowledge and abilities that enable professionals to employ green technologies and processes efficiently. This also includes the transversal knowledge, values, and attitudes that support them in making environmentally friendly decisions in their work and personal lives (Kamisa et al., n.d.; Sern et al., 2018). With these, an assessment of the different and additional skills that can be incorporated into the workforce is required. Since the movement of the economy towards the green transition will have its effect on most occupations and professions to some degree, reinforcing the reskilling and retraining to amplify the green economy initiatives is therefore required.

In terms of transforming the economy and the society in alignment with the concept of sustainable development, **Technical and Vocational Education and Training (TVET)** plays a pivotal role in empowering the people by improving their capacity to effectively address environment and development issues. In addition to these, TVET promotes resource efficiency in key sectors such as construction, manufacturing, transportation, logistics, hospitality services, waste management, and agriculture. The term **Greening TVET** is a systemic approach that integrates environmental sustainability principles into the TVET training systems (UNESCO-UNEVOC, 2015; Majumdar, 2013). This is to ensure that the skills development processes are adherent to the requirements of a sustainable green economy. This extends to institutional practices, training delivery, industry collaboration, and policy framework that will promote sustainable and inclusive development outcomes.

As a strategic mechanism in equipping learners with both the job-specific technical competencies and broader sustainability-oriented capabilities, Greening TVET is seen as a catalyst for the evolving demands of green industries. Emphasis is placed on lifelong learning, adaptability, and innovation to effectively prepare the workforce to skillfully navigate the uncertainties brought about by climate change and economic transformation. Since then, various initiatives have been carried out within the region to further advance the greening of its TVET systems. This includes curriculum restructuring, competency-based training reforms, and strengthened partnerships between the industry and academia. These undertakings aim to

ensure that the skills development are relevant, responsive, and inclusive to efficiently and effectively address the needs of the vulnerable populations which unfortunately are disproportionately affected by the environmental and economic transition.

Nevertheless, despite the many advancements with both the technology integration and the full implementation of the green paradigm in the Asia-Pacific region, the Greening TVET initiatives remain uneven in terms of implementation due to the growing disparities in institutional capacities, resource availability, and policy coherence. This exposes the need for a more coordinated regional approach that will foster knowledge sharing, capacity building and harmonization of national standards in order to strengthen the effectiveness of the TVET systems in empowering the green transition.

3. METHODOLOGY

3.1 Research Design

This study employed a **descriptive-exploratory research design** to examine the integration of green skills, sustainability, digital competencies, and inclusive practices of TVET systems within the Asia-Pacific countries. This enabled a systematic assessment of the institutional readiness, curriculum integration, skill gaps, policy support, industry collaboration, and implementation challenges that are related to the Greening TVET transformation.

With the emerging and evolving nature of the green skills development, the utilization of the descriptive-exploratory approach enabled the identification of patterns, gaps, and institutional practices without testing causal relationships. This research is anchored on the premise that Greening TVET transformation is at varying stages of implementation across the region which requires exploratory assessment to inform future policy and program development. Moreover, the conceptual framing of the study was drawn from the sustainability transition perspectives and TVET systems development literature. This further emphasized the role of education and training institutions in supporting green economy transitions through skills development, innovation, and inclusive capacity building.

3.2 Study Context

Industrial restructuring, climate change, and the shift toward low-carbon and digital economies are continuously shaping the regional landscape through the rapid economic, environmental, and technological transitions. This paved the way for the increase with the demand for a future-ready workforce that is equipped with green skills, digital competencies, climate-resilient knowledge, and inclusive values that are fortified with the sustainable development priorities.

In this defining situation, TVET institutions are instrumental in enabling workforce development. This is through the successful integration of sustainability-oriented curricula, strengthening of industry partnerships, and promotion of applied research and innovation in green technologies. However, the extent of the implementation remains uneven which is attributed to the differences in institutional capacity, policy maturity, resource availability, and industry engagement.

Looking through the program-based context, this study drew insights from a purposive group of TVET professionals who are directly working in Greening TVET activities in their respective organizations. The perspectives that were provided by the respondents provided an informed, multi-country view of how green

skills, sustainability practices, digital transformation, and inclusiveness are being integrated into the TVET systems across the APAC region.

3.3 Data Sources

In order to provide a holistic perspective on the integration of green skills, sustainability, digital competencies, and inclusive practices in TVET systems across Asia-Pacific countries, this study drew upon multiple sources of evidence that offer a comprehensive understanding of current institutional practices, skill gaps, industry collaboration, and implementation challenges within the Greening TVET transformation.

- **Primary data:** A structured survey was administered to the participants of the CPSC Regional Program on *Promoting Green Research, Green Skills, Sustainability, and Inclusiveness in TVET Systems of Asia-Pacific Countries* that was conducted from February 23-27, 2026 in Bangkok, Thailand. The survey gathered the respondents' demographic profiles and their assessments of the key thematic areas to include the following: institutional practices in promoting green skills and sustainability, perceived skill gaps in green, digital, and inclusive competencies, industry-institution collaboration practices, the extent of green skills training leading to employment or income-generating opportunities, and the key challenges in implementing Greening TVET initiatives. A total of 15 participants took part in the study which represented a cross-section of TVET institutions, government agencies, and training organizations across a number of Asia-Pacific member countries of the Colombo Plan Staff College (CPSC).
- **Secondary data:** Relevant program documents, regional policy frameworks, and institutional reports were also reviewed to establish a contextual understanding of green skills development, TVET transformation, and sustainability-oriented education systems. In addition, international policy documents and reports from organizations such as the United Nations Environment Programme, UNESCO-UNEVOC, International Labour Organization, and related global climate and green economy frameworks were analyzed to situate the study within broader regional and global sustainability agendas (United Nations, n.d.; UNESCO-UNEVOC, n.d.; International Labour Organization, 2019; World Bank, 2021). These sources helped contextualize how policy environments, institutional capacities, and labor market transitions influence the implementation of green and inclusive TVET systems in the Asia-Pacific region.

4. SAMPLING AND DATA COLLECTION

This study adopted a purposive sampling method in which the respondents were selected based on their direct involvement in green skills development, sustainability integration, digital competencies, and inclusive practices within the TVET institutions across the CPSC member countries. Specifically, the respondents were participants of the CPSC Regional Program on *Promoting Green Research, Green Skills, Sustainability, and Inclusiveness in TVET Systems of Asia-Pacific Countries* conducted in Bangkok, Thailand.

By engaging key stakeholders who are actively involved in training delivery, curriculum development, institutional management, and policy-related functions, the researchers were able to gather informed insights on institutional practices in Greening TVET, perceived skill gaps, industry collaboration mechanisms, employment relevance of green skills training, and implementation challenges in advancing sustainable and inclusive TVET systems.

The following section presents the demographic profile of the respondents who participated in the study.

**Table 1. Demographic Profile of Survey Respondents
(n=15)**

Variable	Categories	Frequency
Gender	Female	5
	Male	10
Age	30-39	4
	40-49	6
	50-59	4
	60-69	1
Country	Bangladesh	1
	Bhutan	1
	India	2
	Malaysia	2
	Maldives	1
	Myanmar	1
	Pakistan	2
	Philippines	2
	Singapore	2
	Sri Lanka	1
Organization/Institution	Center of Excellence in Networking & Information Technology	1
	Government Technical Institute (Myingyan)	1
	Institute of Technical Education	1
	Ministry	1

	Ministry of Education	1
	National Skills Development Authority (NSDA)	1
	National Vocational and Technical Training Commission (NAVTTTC)	1
	National Institute of Technical Teachers Training and Research N(NITTTR), Bhopal	1
	National Institute of Technical Teachers Training and Research N(NITTTR), Chandigarh	1
	Politeknik Merlimau Melaka	1
	Politeknik Sultan Idris Shah	1
	Republic Polytechnic	1
	Technical Education and Skills Development Authority (TESDA), Regional Training Center - Kabankalan Vocational Training Center (RTC-KPVTC)	1
	Technical Education and Skills Development Authority (TESDA), Regional Training Center - Lipa-Laguna Development Authority Provincial Training Center	1
	University College of Anuradhapura, University	1

	of Vocational Technology - Sri Lanka	
Designation	Deputy Director	1
	Deputy Manager	1
	Deputy Secretary	1
	Managing Director	1
	Principal	1
	Academic Staff	5
	Program Analyst	1
	Senior Political Director	1
	Senior TESD Specialist	1
	TESD Specialist II	1

The study involved 15 respondents who successfully completed the structured survey. Despite its modest number, the sample reflects the exploratory and in-depth nature of this study by emphasizing analytical richness rather than statistical generalization. The engaged participants represent a cross-section of TVET professionals from various Asia-Pacific institutions including technical institutes, polytechnics, universities, and national training and government agencies across Bangladesh, Bhutan, India, Malaysia, Maldives, Myanmar, Pakistan, the Philippines, Singapore, and Sri Lanka. The sample includes academic staff, lecturers, senior technical specialists, institutional leaders, and policymakers with a balanced gender distribution and an age range spanning from 30 to 69 years.

The data were collected directly from the respondents to ensure an accurate representation of their experiences, perspectives, and insights on institutional practices in promoting green skills, sustainability, digital integration, and inclusive approaches within TVET systems. This method enabled an effective examination of institutional green practices, perceived skill gaps, industry collaboration mechanisms, the employment relevance of green skills training, and the structural and policy-related challenges influencing the implementation of Greening TVET initiatives across the region.

5. RESULTS AND ANALYSIS

This section presents the key findings of the study on the integration of green skills, sustainability, digital competencies, and inclusive practices in TVET systems across selected Asia-Pacific countries. Drawing primarily on the results of the online survey that were administered to 15 respondents, the discussion examines institutional practices in promoting green and sustainable TVET, perceived skill gaps, industry-institution collaboration mechanisms, the employment relevance of green skills training, and the key implementation challenges that were encountered in advancing Greening TVET initiatives.

The results are further interpreted within the broader context of regional TVET transformation frameworks, sustainability transition agendas, and global green economy policies. This allows for an assessment of the extent to which existing institutional systems and practices enable or constrain the effective integration of green skills, digital transformation, and inclusive approaches across diverse TVET contexts in the Asia-Pacific region.

Figure 1. Effectiveness of Institutional TVET System in Equipping Learners with Renewable Energy, Eco-Manufacturing, and Sustainable Agriculture

Figure 1 highlights the respondents' perceptions on the **effectiveness of their TVET systems in equipping learners with green technical skills specifically in areas such as renewable energy, eco-manufacturing, and sustainable agriculture**. The findings indicate a generally positive assessment with the majority of responses falling within the "very effective" category. Eight respondents (53%) rated the system as very effective while four respondents (27%) perceived it as moderately effective. In addition, two respondents (13%) categorized their TVET systems as extremely effective, and only one respondent (7%) considered theirs as slightly effective. Overall, the results suggest that the TVET institutions demonstrate a strong but still developing capacity in terms of integrating green technical competencies.

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This reflects the ongoing progress that the CPSC member countries are undertaking towards strengthening the sustainability-oriented skills within their respective TVET system.

Figure 2. Effectiveness of Institutional TVET System in Equipping Learners with Circular Economy and Resource Efficiency

In terms of the respondents' **perceptions regarding the effectiveness of their TVET systems in equipping learners with circular economy and resource efficiency skills**, Figure 2 indicates a generally favorable assessment with responses concentrated in the moderate to high effectiveness categories. Eight respondents (53%) reported their institutions as very effective while five respondents (33%) perceived them as moderately effective. In contrast, two respondents (13%) rated their TVET system as slightly effective, and no responses were recorded for the “extremely effective” category. Overall, the results suggest that while circular economy and resource efficiency competencies are being integrated into TVET provision, there remains room for further strengthening to achieve more consistent and advanced implementation across the regional TVET institutions.

Figure 3. Effectiveness of Institutional TVET System in Equipping Learners with Climate-Resilient Practices and Environmental Responsibility

Figure 3 showcases the respondents’ perspective as regards to the **effectiveness of their TVET systems in equipping learners with climate-resilient practices and environmental responsibility**. The outcomes reveal a generally strong assessment with most responses clustered in the higher effectiveness categories. Eight respondents (53%) evaluated their TVET system as very effective whereas six respondents (40%) appraised theirs as moderately effective. In addition, one respondent (7%) rated the system as extremely effective, and no responses were recorded for the lower effectiveness categories. These results indicate that the TVET institutions demonstrate a solid capacity in integrating climate-resilience and environmental responsibility into their training programs. However, continued enhancement is still needed to strengthen advanced implementation and wider consistency across institutions.

Figure 4. Effectiveness of Institutional TVET System in Equipping Learners with Green Research and Innovation

As regards to the **effectiveness of TVET systems in equipping learners with green research and innovation skills** (Figure 4), the survey participants provided a generally positive assessment with responses distributed across moderate to high effectiveness levels. Six respondents (40%) categorized their institutions as moderately effective while five (33%) perceived their organization as very effective. Moreover, three respondents (20%) rated the systems as extremely effective while one respondent (7%) considered theirs as not effective. These suggest that while green research and innovation competencies are increasingly being integrated into TVET programs, there remains a need to further strengthen institutional support and research capacity to ensure more consistent and higher-level implementation across institutions.

Figure 5. Effectiveness of Institutional TVET System in Equipping Learners with Digital-Green Skills, Artificial Intelligence, Internet of Things, Augmented/Virtual Reality, and Smart Technologies for Sustainability

Figure 5 presents the respondents' perceptions regarding the **effectiveness of their TVET systems in equipping learners with digital-green skills including artificial intelligence, Internet of Things, augmented reality/virtual reality, and other smart technologies for sustainability**. The findings indicate a balanced but moderately positive assessment across the effectiveness scale. Five respondents (33%) rated their institutions as moderately effective while another five respondents (33%) perceived theirs as very effective. In addition, three respondents (20%) rated their system as extremely effective while one respondent (7%) considered it as slightly effective. Lastly, one respondent (7%) rated it as not effective at all. The results expose that even though digital-green competencies are being integrated into TVET systems, their implementation remains uneven, highlighting the need for further strengthening in terms of infrastructure, capacity, and instructional integration.

Figure 6. Effectiveness of Institutional TVET System in Equipping Learners with Inclusive and Gender-Responsive Practices

With regard to the respondents' perspective regarding the **effectiveness of their TVET systems in equipping learners with inclusive and gender-responsive practices** (Figure 6), the results reveal a generally strong positive assessment with responses concentrated in the higher effectiveness categories. Six respondents (40%) rated their institutions as extremely effective while four respondents (27%) rated theirs as very effective. Moreover, three respondents (20%) reported their TVET system as moderately effective, one (7%) as slightly effective, and another one (7%) as not effective. This reveals that inclusivity and gender responsiveness are relatively well-integrated within TVET systems, although there remains a need to further address gaps to ensure more consistent implementation across all institutions.

Figure 7. Effectiveness of Institutional TVET System in Equipping Learners with Policy and Governance Awareness for Sustainability

Figure 7 underscores the **effectiveness of the regional TVET systems in equipping learners with policy and governance awareness for sustainability**. The results show a generally favorable assessment with responses concentrated in the moderate to high effectiveness categories. Seven respondents (47%) rated their institutions as very effective while five respondents (33%) perceived them as moderately effective. Additionally, two respondents (13%) assessed the TVET system as extremely effective, and one respondent (7%) considered it as slightly effective. This illustrates that policy and governance-related sustainability competencies are being integrated into TVET provision at a reasonably strong level. Even so, further enhancement is still needed to strengthen deeper institutional embedding and consistency across different TVET settings.

Figure 8. Institutional Readiness in Implementing and Adopting Green, Digital, and Inclusive TVET Reforms

In terms of the TVET institutions' readiness to implement and adopt green, digital, and inclusive TVET reforms (Figure 8), the outcomes of the survey indicate that most institutions are still in the transitional phase of development. Nine respondents (60%) reported that their institutions are in the developing stage while four respondents (27%) indicated that their systems are moderately established. Only two respondents (13%) assessed their institutions as being in the advanced stage of readiness. These results suggest that while progress toward integrating green, digital, and inclusive reforms is evident, most TVET institutions are still strengthening foundational systems, capacities, and structures to fully operationalize these reforms.

Table 2. Perceived Skill Gaps in Green, Digital, and Inclusive Competencies among TVET Institutions

Skill Gaps	Frequency	% of Respondents
Circular Economy/Resource Efficiency Skills	9	60
Climate-Resilient Practices	9	60
Green Technical Skills	8	53
Green Research and Innovation	8	53
Digital-Green/Smart Technology Skills	5	33
Policy and Governance Skills	3	20
Inclusive/Gender-Responsive Skills	2	13

Table 2 presents the perceived skill gaps in green, digital, and inclusive competencies among TVET institutions. The findings show that Circular Economy/Resource Efficiency Skills and Climate-Resilient Practices are the most prominent gaps, both reported by 60% (9) of the respondents, indicating a strong need to strengthen sustainability-oriented competencies in TVET programs. Green Technical Skills and Green Research and Innovation follow, each identified by 53% (8) of the respondents, suggesting moderate gaps in applied sustainability knowledge and innovation capacity. Digital-Green/Smart Technology Skills were reported by 33% (5), highlighting a continuing gap in integrating emerging technologies such as AI and IoT into sustainability learning. Policy and Governance Skills were identified by 20% (3), while Inclusive/Gender-Responsive Skills recorded the lowest gap at 13% (2). Overall, the results indicate that while foundational green competencies are partially addressed, stronger emphasis is still needed on circular economy practices, climate resilience, and digital-green integration within TVET systems.

Table 3. Institutional Practices Supporting Green Skills, Sustainability, and Inclusive TVET Development among Respondents

Institutional Practice	Frequency	% of Respondents
Green Campus Initiatives	12	80
Green/Sustainable Curriculum Modules	12	80
Digital Tools Integrated into Sustainability Education	8	53
Green Research Initiatives	8	53
Low-Cost Sustainable Technology Projects	8	53
Industry Partnerships for Women, Disadvantaged Learners, or Marginalized Groups	3	20

Table 3 exhibits the **institutional practices supporting green skills, sustainability, and inclusive TVET development** among the respondents. The findings demonstrate that Green Campus Initiatives and Green/Sustainable Curriculum Modules are the most widely implemented practices with both reported by 80% (12) of the respondents. This reflects a strong institutional commitment to embedding sustainability within both campus operations and curriculum design. Digital Tools Integrated into Sustainability Education, Green Research Initiatives, and Low-Cost Sustainable Technology Projects were each reported by 53% (8) of the respondents which suggest a moderate level of integration of innovation, applied research, and practical sustainability solutions across institutions. Meanwhile, Industry Partnerships for Women, Disadvantaged Learners, or Marginalized Groups was selected by only 20% (3) of the respondents. This indicates that inclusive and equity-focused collaboration with industry remains relatively limited. Overall, the results suggest that while sustainability-related institutional practices are becoming well established, inclusive partnership mechanisms still require further strengthening within TVET systems.

Table 4. Institutional and Industry Collaboration Practices Supporting Green Skills and Sustainability Development in TVET

Institute-Industry Collaboration Practice	Frequency	% of Respondents
Internship Programs	7	58
Industry-Led Workshop/Training	6	50
Collaboration on Sustainability/Green Innovation Projects	6	50
Joint R&D Projects on Green Technology/Sustainability	5	42
Mentorship Programs	2	17
Staff Attachment, Course Feedback, Module Feedback	1	8
TVET Authority, Policy and Monitoring, NCS Developing	1	8

Table 4 describes the **institutional and industry collaboration practices supporting green skills and sustainability development in TVET**. The findings reveal that Internship Programs are the most common form of collaboration as reported by 58% (7) of the respondents. This indicates that work-based learning remains a key mechanism for linking learners with industry exposure. Industry-Led Workshops/Training and Collaboration on Sustainability/Green Innovation Projects were each reported by 50% (6) of the respondents thereby, reflecting a growing but still moderate level of industry engagement in sustainability-focused capacity building and applied innovation. Joint Research & Development (R&D) Projects on Green Technology/Sustainability were identified by 42% (5) of the respondents. This reinforces the fact that research collaboration between TVET institutions and industry is emerging but not yet widely established. Meanwhile, Mentorship Programs (17%), Staff Attachment and Feedback Mechanisms (8%), and TVET Authority-linked policy and monitoring initiatives (8%) were the least reported thus, indicating limited structured long-term collaboration and policy-industry feedback loops. These findings reflect that while foundational industry engagement is present, deeper collaborative mechanisms for green skills development remain underdeveloped.

Figure 9. Perceived Employment and Livelihood Outcomes of Green Skills Training Programs

Figure 9 presents the respondents' perceptions on the extent to which **training programs with green skills in their institutions lead to tangible employment or income-generating prospects**. The findings showcase that most respondents, 60% (9), believe that such programs contribute to employment outcomes to a moderate extent. At the same time, 20% (3) indicated a small extent while 7% (1) each reported a great extent and a very great extent. In contrast, 7% (1) of the respondents stated that these programs do not lead to any tangible employment or income-generating opportunities. Taken together, the results indicate that green skills training is beginning to generate employability benefits although its impact remains largely moderate. This demonstrates that stronger alignment between TVET programs and green labor market opportunities is still needed to fully translate training into sustainable employment and income generation outcomes.

Table 5. Challenges in the Implementation of Green, Digital, and Inclusive TVET Programs

Challenge	Frequency	% of Respondents
Lack of Funding/Resources	11	73
Limited Faculty Expertise in Green/Digital/Inclusive Skills	9	60
Insufficient Infrastructure for Green Innovation	6	40
Weak Industry Linkages in Green Sectors	8	53
Policy/Regulatory Limitations	6	40
Resistance to Change	4	27
Low Learner Motivation/Participation	3	20
Low Learner Motivation for Non-related Courses	1	7

Table 5 highlights the **challenges in the implementation of green, digital, and inclusive TVET programs**. The outcomes of the survey indicate that the most critical constraint is the lack of funding and resources covering 73% (11) of the respondents. This highlights a major structural limitation in scaling sustainability-oriented initiatives. This is followed by limited faculty expertise in green, digital, and inclusive skills which was identified by 60% (9) of the respondents, and weak industry linkages in green sectors covering 53% (8) of the respondents. These details point to the capacity and ecosystem-related gaps in implementation. Insufficient infrastructure for green innovation and policy/regulatory limitations were each reported by 40% (6) thereby, indicating institutional and systemic barriers that further constrain program effectiveness. Meanwhile, resistance to change was identified by 27% (4) of respondents while low learner motivation/participation was reported by 20% (3). The least chosen challenge was low learner motivation for non-related courses at 7% (1). Overall, the results suggest that financial constraints, capacity gaps, and weak industry engagement are the primary barriers hindering the effective implementation of green, digital, and inclusive TVET reforms.

6. DISCUSSION

The findings of this study provide important insights as to how TVET institutions across the participating Asia-Pacific countries are integrating green, digital, and inclusive competencies within their systems in response to the global shift toward sustainable development and the green economy agenda (UNESCO, 2017; ILO, 2019). Overall, the results indicate that the regional TVET systems are still in the transitional phase of the green transformation in which foundational structures are already in place but the implementation remains uneven across TVET institutions.

The results show that sustainability-related competencies are generally perceived as moderately to very effectively integrated into TVET systems. Green technical skills, circular economy competencies, climate-resilient practices, and policy awareness for sustainability are increasingly embedded in training and curriculum frameworks. This reflects the broader global efforts toward aligning education and skills development with the green transition and climate action priorities emphasized in international climate frameworks such as the Paris Agreement and subsequent COP processes (UNFCCC, 2015; United Nations, 2025). Among the different skill areas, inclusive and gender-responsive practices appear to be relatively more established. This exposes a stronger institutional attention to equity dimensions in line with global calls for just and inclusive transitions (ILO, 2019; UNDP, 2025).

Despite these developments, significant skill gaps remain particularly in circular economy/resource efficiency and climate-resilient practices. These findings align with global literature emphasizing that while awareness of green transition is increasing, applied competencies in resource efficiency, circular systems, and climate adaptation remain underdeveloped in many developing TVET systems (UNESCO-UNEVOC, 2018; Wambura, 2024). Green technical skills and green research and innovation also remain moderate gaps thus, indicating that innovation-driven sustainability transformation is still emerging rather than fully institutionalized.

Digital-green skills and policy and governance competencies are also identified as gaps, reflecting the early stage of integration of Industry 4.0 and emerging Industry 5.0 technologies into sustainability-oriented education systems (Zilberstein, 2023; Quimba et al., 2023). This suggests that while digital transformation is advancing globally, its convergence with sustainability in TVET systems is still evolving unevenly across institutions.

Institutional practices further illustrate this mixed progress. Strong implementation is evident in green campus initiatives and curriculum integration which reflects alignment with global greening TVET frameworks that emphasize institutional sustainability and curriculum reform (UNESCO, 2017). Moderate engagement in digital tools, research initiatives, and low-cost green innovation projects further supports the growing shift toward applied sustainability education. However, limited industry partnerships for marginalized groups indicate that inclusive dimensions of green TVET remain less developed, despite global emphasis on just transition and equity-centered skills development (ILO, 2019).

Industry collaboration patterns show that engagement is still largely concentrated in internships, workshops, and training-based interactions. While these are important for work-based learning, the limited presence of joint R&D, mentorship, and policy feedback mechanisms suggests that industry-TVET collaboration remains largely transactional rather than innovation-driven. This finding is consistent with regional studies highlighting weak institutional-industry linkages as a key barrier in greening TVET systems in Asia-Pacific contexts (ESCAP, 2021; UNEVOC, n.d.).

In terms of outcomes, the moderate perception of employment and income-generation impacts reveals that green TVET systems are still in the process of aligning with evolving green labor markets. This aligns with global evidence that green job creation is expanding but remains uneven across sectors and regions, particularly in developing economies where green industry ecosystems are still emerging (International Labour Organization, 2019; World Bank insights cited in UNEVOC, n.d.).

The study also identifies key implementation challenges with funding constraints, limited faculty expertise, and weak industry linkages emerging as the most significant barriers. These findings are consistent with prior studies emphasizing that capacity limitations, infrastructure gaps, and policy fragmentation are major constraints in scaling up green and inclusive TVET reforms (UNESCO-UNEVOC, 2018; Ajmone Marsan & Litania, 2023). Nevertheless, the evidence suggests that challenges are structural rather than conceptual, requiring systemic interventions rather than isolated reforms.

7. CONCLUSION

This study demonstrates that TVET systems across the participating Asia-Pacific countries are gradually advancing toward the integration of green, digital, and inclusive competencies in response to global sustainability and climate action imperatives (UNFCCC, 2015; United Nations, 2025). However, this transformation remains uneven reflecting differences in institutional capacity, resource availability, and industry engagement.

While foundational progress is evident, particularly in green curriculum integration and institutional sustainability initiatives, the development of advanced competencies such as circular economy practices, climate-resilient skills, and digital-green integration remains limited. This highlights the ongoing need to strengthen alignment between TVET systems and global green transition frameworks including the circular economy and green growth agenda (Martínez, 2024; UNEVOC, 2018).

Moreover, although inclusive practices are emerging, they are not yet fully embedded within the institutional and industry collaboration structures. This suggests that the social dimension of the green transition requires further strengthening in line with just transition principles (ILO, 2019; UNDP, 2025). The moderate employment outcomes further indicate that green TVET systems are still developing their linkage with green labor markets, which remain uneven across the region.

Collectively, the study underscores that the primary barriers to effective green TVET transformation are structural, specifically funding limitations, faculty capacity gaps, and weak industry engagement. Addressing these challenges requires sustained investment, targeted capacity-building, and stronger multi-stakeholder collaboration across TVET institutions, industry, and policy actors.

Ultimately, strengthening these dimensions will be essential for enabling TVET systems in the Asia-Pacific region to fully realize their role as catalysts for sustainable, inclusive, and resilient development in the context of the global green and digital transition.

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